

A HOLISTIC APPROACH TO SPACE SUSTAINABILITY: CLOSING THE LOOP BETWEEN GLOBAL SPACE HEALTH INDICATORS AND LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

This paper presents an integrated framework that combines Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), utilizing the Strathclyde Space Systems Database (SSSD), with the Network model for Space Sustainability (NESSY) to evaluate space sustainability from both terrestrial and orbital perspectives. NESSY simulates orbital debris dynamics under various policy scenarios, while the LCA assesses environmental impacts across all mission phases on Earth. The framework produces Sustainability Indices that quantify both system-wide and mission-specific impacts. Two case studies demonstrate the framework's potential to inform environmentally responsible space mission design. The results underscore the critical role of collision avoidance and end-of-life disposal policies. Overall, the framework supports evidence-based decision-making to mitigate long-term environmental degradation in both Earth-based and orbital domains.

1. Introduction

The space sector is currently one of the fastest-growing industries, leading to a continuous rise in the number of resident space objects. Collisions among these objects can generate debris clouds, potentially initiating a cascade effect, commonly known as the Kessler Syndrome, that could render certain orbital regions unusable for future missions.¹ Large satellite constellations significantly contribute to the evolution of the space debris environment,² while the presence of untracked debris further elevates the risk of frequent and hazardous collisions.³ To ensure the long-term sustainability of space operations, it is imperative that mission planners and regulatory bodies incorporate environmental considerations during the design and approval phases of space missions.

To address this challenge, the NESSY is introduced. NESSY models the space environment as a dynamic temporal network, where each node represents a group of space objects of a specific type, and the links capture their interactions. This network-based approach enables the analysis of the temporal evolution of object interactions and provides insights into the overall health of the orbital environment through its topological and dynamical properties. Complementing this orbital perspective, the SSSD offers an LCA framework tailored specifically for the space sector. The SSSD enables the quantification of environmental, social, and economic impacts across all phases of a space mission. This Earth-based assessment tool supports stakeholders in evaluating and minimizing negative impacts, thereby promoting responsible and sustainable space activities that align with broader goals of environmental stewardship and societal well-being.⁴

This paper proposes an integrated framework that combines NESSY and the SSSD to enable a comprehensive, end-to-end assessment of space mission impacts across both orbital and terrestrial domains. The study makes significant advancements to the foundational work reported by Wang (2024),⁵ and addresses two primary objectives. Objective 1 (OB1) involves a quantitative evaluation of the trade-off for the STRATHcube constellation between omitting the propulsion system, to reduce environmental impact, and including it to enable critical functions such as collision avoidance and end-of-life disposal. Objective 2 (OB2) focuses on analysing the evolution of the space environment and assessing how different launch traffic models influence both Earth-based and orbital environmental impacts.

2. Strathclyde Space System Database

The SSSD is a specialised database developed at the University of Strathclyde to support process-based LCA tailored to the specific needs of the space sector.⁴ While this paper focuses on the application of LCA, the overarching ambition of the SSSD project is to facilitate the transition towards a comprehensive Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) framework. The database was initially created to address the absence of space-specific LCA datasets prior to the release of the European Space Agency (ESA) LCA Database, with a scope that extends beyond geographical boundaries. Ultimately, the tool can be used to facilitate the integration of eco-design and Life Cycle Engineering (LCE) principles into concurrent engineering practices for space mission development.

2.1 Impact Category Scores Computation

While the SSSD supports multiple assessment methodologies, its default output presents results at the midpoint level, based on the IPAT equation. Midpoint indicator results are calculated as:

$$IR_c = \sum_s CF_{cs} \cdot m_s \quad (1)$$

where IR_c is the indicator result for impact category c , CF_{cs} is the characterisation factor linking intervention s to category c , and m_s is the magnitude of intervention s .

The full set of indicators are primarily based on the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) approach.⁶ This includes: *Acidification (AC)*, *Climate Change (CC)*, *Ecotoxicity*, *Freshwater (EX-FW)*, *Eutrophication (Freshwater, Marine, Terrestrial – EP-FW, EP-M, EP-T)*, *Human Toxicity (Cancer and Non-Cancer – HT-C, HT-NC)*, *Ionising Radiation (IC)*, *Land Use (LU)*, *Ozone Depletion (OD)*, *Particulate Matter (PM)*, *Photochemical Oxidant Formation (POF)*, *Resource Use (Fossil Fuels and Minerals/Metals – RU-FF, RU-MM)*, and *Water Use (WU)*. However, to expand upon the existing suite of Earth-based indicators, adaptations to the PEF method have been introduced in the SSSD to better reflect the space sector's unique characteristics. This includes the definition of additional impact categories and new/updated characterisation factors for specific impact categories related to launcher emissions and re-entry.

To facilitate streamlined decision-making within concurrent design environments, the SSSD also supports generating a single score using a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) approach based on Multi-Attribute Value Theory (MAVT), which is particularly useful for constellation assessments. The overall score is computed as:

$$v(a) = \sum_{i=1}^I w_i \cdot v_i(a) \quad (2)$$

where $v(a)$ is the overall score for system a , w_i is the weight assigned to impact category i , and $v_i(a)$ is the performance of system a in that category.

Whilst various single score methodologies for space LCA are beginning to develop^{7,8} for environmental criteria within the SSSD, the default single score method applied relates to the PEF approach for normalisation and weighting based on EU-27 consumption data,^{9,10} with the planetary boundaries approach used as an alternative.¹¹

2.2 Integration of the Space Environmental Impact into LCA

Historically, LCAs in the space sector have primarily concentrated on Earth-based environmental impacts. Notable exceptions include the work of Thibaut Maury,¹² who developed a framework to address the risks associated with long-lived orbital debris. However, this approach has not been formally adopted by the ESA. Instead, ESA manages space debris through its Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines.¹³ Additionally, the technical complexity involved, particularly concerning ESA's MASTER tool, has hindered broader integration of debris impact assessment within standard LCA practices.

2.2.1 Orbital Impact Indicators

To overcome this limitation, two new space-based impact categories have been introduced into the SSSD and will be added to the default impact assessment framework. New environmental indicators were created to reflect spacecraft operations at varying altitudes and inclinations, referring to data provided by NESSY. The new orbital impact indicators include:

- *OR-AP (Orbital Risk)*: Represents the induced risk of the objects in a particular orbital regime with the rest of the space environment. This is a unit-less quantity ranging from 0 to 1, quantified using percolation theory.

- *OR-DR (Orbital Space Use and Depletion)*: Measures the spatial density of spacecrafts in a particular orbital regime, expressed in units of objects/m³.

These indicators are then passed through the MCDA module to compare the relative criticality of Earth-based vs. space-based impacts, addressing the emerging Space Sustainability Paradox.¹⁴

3. Network model for Space Sustainability (NESSY)

Network model for Space Sustainability (NESSY) was proposed to model the space environment as a stochastic dynamics model, where each node is a group of objects, belonging to a given class, and their relationship is represented by stochastic links. The stochastic dynamics network model of the space environment is introduced, followed by the percolation dynamics of the space environment, which quantifies the local/global health of the space environment. This provides a foundation for defining orbital impact indicators, offering a novel measure of orbital risk and supporting long-term sustainability assessments of space activities.

3.1 A Stochastic Dynamic Network Model of the Space Environment

The space environment is modelled with a network consisting of n nodes. Each node S_i represents $x_{S_i}(t_k)$ objects of a given class S at time t_k . Four species are considered: Payloads (P), Upper stages (U), Fragments (F) and Non-maneuvrable satellites (N), therefore, $\mathcal{S} = \{P, U, N, F\}$. Each class is further partitioned according to the altitude shell and inclination interval to which a given group of objects belongs. The number of objects $x_{S_i}(t_k)$ can change because of collisions, explosions, natural decay due to atmospheric drag, Post-Mission Disposal (PMD) strategies, operational lifetime duration, and new launches. Once the structure and topology of the network are defined one can derive the stochastic evolutionary equations, governing the evolution of each node P_i , U_i , N_i and F_i . Let $\mathbf{X}_k = [x_{P_1}, x_{U_1}, x_{N_1}, x_{F_1}, \dots, x_{P_n}, x_{U_n}, x_{N_n}, x_{F_n}]^T$ represent the vector that contains all the nodes x_{S_i} , with $S \in \{P, U, N, F\}$ and $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then a more compact form of the evolutionary equations is:

$$\mathbf{X}_{k+1} = \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{Y}(\mathbf{X}_k) + \mathbf{g}(t_k) \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{Y}(\mathbf{X}_k)$ contains the interactions among nodes (collisions and orbit change) and satellite failures, while $\mathbf{g}(t_k)$ contains all time dependent terms, such as the launch traffic model $\Lambda_i(t_k)$. For further details on each component of the model, please refer to the paper.¹⁵

3.2 The Percolation Dynamics of the Space Environment

Percolation is quantified differently for different networks and has its own dynamics. Together with percolation one can compute the speed of diffusion which measures how fast events are spreading.¹⁶ The connectivity between nodes represents the degree of interaction or the probability that two species or communities interact. The connection rate between node S_i and node S_j within time Δt_k , denoted by $\chi_{S_i S_j}$, depends on: the collision rate between the nodes ($\chi_{S_i S_j}^C$), the rate of the fragments generated from node S_i flowing to node S_j ($\chi_{S_i S_j}^{\mathcal{F}, F}$), the rate of an object flowing from node S_i to node S_j due to the natural decay ($\chi_{S_i S_j}^{\mathcal{F}, D}$), and the rate of an object flowing from node S_i to node S_j due to the failure of PMD ($\chi_{S_i S_j}^{\mathcal{F}, PMD}$).

The event can be generated by one node and affect the other or can be due to the interaction of both nodes. The total flow rate defining a link from node S_i to node S_j is:

$$\chi_{S_i S_j} = \chi_{S_i S_j}^C + \chi_{S_i S_j}^{\mathcal{F}, F} + \chi_{S_i S_j}^{\mathcal{F}, D} + \chi_{S_i S_j}^{\mathcal{F}, PMD} \quad (4)$$

If only collision-related links are considered, then $\chi_{S_i S_j} = \chi_{S_i S_j}^C + \chi_{S_i S_j}^{\mathcal{F}, F}$. In order to account for the spatial distribution of nodes across multiple sites and the flow of the consequences of events across different parts of the space environment the expression is defined:

$$p_{P_i P_j} = 1 - e^{-\Delta t_k \sum_{S_i \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{S_j \in \mathcal{S}} \chi_{S_i S_j}} \quad (5)$$

and,

$$\delta_{P_i P_j}(\rho) = p_{P_i P_j} \geq \rho \quad (6)$$

which is different from zero if the site P_i and P_j are connected.

In a directed graph G_ρ , the propagation of the effects of events happening in a given orbit site can be quantified via the reachability matrix $\mathbf{R}_c(G_\rho)$. Each entry (i, j) of this matrix is 1 if there is a continuous path from site i to site j ,

indicating that site i has an influence on the evolution of site j . The reachability matrix is the transitive closure of the $n \times n$ connectivity matrix \mathbf{A}_p whose entries are $\delta_{P_i P_j}$. With $\mathbf{R}_c(G_\rho)$ one can define the local connectivity of site i as:

$$\alpha_i^n = \int_0^1 \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n r_{ij}}{n} d\rho \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the global connectivity is:

$$\alpha^n = \frac{\sum_i^n \alpha_i^n}{n} \quad (8)$$

Considering the fragments induced by the collision events, the augmentation of the number of fragments generated by the collisions related to the nodes in the given orbital regime is introduced. Given the estimated number of fragments flowing from node S_i to node F_l generated by the collision between node S_i and node S_j

$$N_{S_i S_j}^{F_l} = \chi_{S_i S_j}^C \Delta t_k \zeta_{S_i S_j} \xi_{S_i S_j}^{F_l} \quad (9)$$

where $\sum_l \xi_{S_i S_j}^{F_l} = 1$. The updated number of objects in node F_l is:

$$x'_{F_l} = x_{F_l} + \sum_{S \in S} \sum_j N_{S_i S_j}^{F_l} \quad (10)$$

Then the updated number of objects in each node is given by:

$$\mathbf{X}'_k = [x_{P_1}, x_{U_1}, x_{N_1}, x'_{F_1}, \dots, x_{P_i}, x_{U_i}, x_{N_i}, x'_{F_i}, \dots, x_{P_n}, x_{U_n}, x_{N_n}, x'_{F_n}]^T \quad (11)$$

Consequently, the impact score α_i^n can be recalculated based on the updated state vector \mathbf{X}'_k , which accounts for the increase in fragment numbers due to the collisions involving nodes in site i .

4. OB1 - Quantitative Evaluation of the CAM&PMD Trade-Off

The first objective involves a quantitative assessment of the environmental trade-offs associated with including or excluding propulsion systems in satellite constellations. While omitting propulsion may reduce the overall environmental footprint, it can compromise critical functions essential to space sustainability, such as collision avoidance manoeuvres (CAM) and post-mission disposal (PMD). This analysis systematically compares the life cycle impacts of constellations with and without propulsion, evaluating how the environmental burden of propulsion hardware and fuel consumption balances against the benefits of improved debris mitigation and operational safety. From this comparison, a set of weighting factors can be derived to reflect the relative significance of various impact categories across both terrestrial and orbital domains. These insights aim to support responsible design decisions by integrating Earth-based and Space-based environmental considerations within a unified sustainability framework.

4.1 STRATHcube Constellation

The STRATHcube satellite has been selected as the reference for designing a constellation mission to compare the two scenarios, due to the availability of detailed design data. It is a 2U CubeSat developed through a student-led initiative at the University of Strathclyde, with mission objectives strongly focused on space sustainability. Originally conceived to demonstrate debris detection and re-entry analysis, the mission has since matured and was recently selected to participate in the European Space Agency's *Fly Your Satellite!* programme.

Figure 1: STRATHcube Satellite Configurations.

4.1.1 Mission Scenarios

For this study, two scenarios were evaluated, each involving a constellation of 1,000 STRATHcube satellites deployed in orbits at altitudes between 800 and 850 km, with inclinations ranging from 40° to 60°. The operational life is assumed to start in June 2029 and last for five years, following a launch using a Falcon 9 launch vehicle. A conservative ride-share cap of 100 CubeSats was considered per launch, requiring a total of 10 launches for each scenario. The constellation layout consists of 20 orbital planes with 50 satellites per plane, ensuring global coverage and even distribution.

The timing and sequence of operations are assumed to be identical in both scenarios and are summarized in the Concept of Operations (CONOPS) diagram shown in Figure 2. The mission phases are defined following the ESA convention, ensuring consistency with standardized space mission lifecycle definitions. In the figure, mission phases governed by LCA assumptions are highlighted in green, while those affected by the NESSY framework are blue, to clearly distinguish the environmental modelling boundaries.

The first scenario considers an updated STRATHcube design, consistent with the latest *Fly Your Satellite!* Baseline Design Review (BDR) and the baseline configuration detailed by Wilson and Vasile,¹⁷ which assumes no collision avoidance manoeuvres (CAM) and includes post-mission disposal (PMD) conducted passively, without any propulsion system. The second scenario presents the same model, but enhanced by the integration of an ExPace cold-gas propulsion system and the GomSpace OBC (On-Board Computer) to enable active CAM and PMD. These configurations are based on consistent design and operational assumptions, ensuring a fair and coherent comparison of the environmental impacts between the two STRATHcube variants. The input parameters used for the two tools applied in this study are detailed in Table 1 and Table 2.

Figure 2: Concept of Operations (CONOPS) for the STRATHcube constellation mission.

Table 1: NESSY Data

	w/o CAM&PMD	w/ CAM&PMD
Altitude [km]	800–850	800–850
Inclination [degrees]	40–60	40–60
Number of satellites	1000	1000
Mass [kg]	2.726075	4.046075
Size [cm]	20	20
Lifetime [year]	5	5
CAM Success [%]	0	99.9
PMD Failure [%]	100	5

Table 2: SSSD LCA Data

	w/o CAM&PMD	w/ CAM&PMD
Number of satellites	1000	1000
Mass [kg]	2.726075	4.046075
Launcher	Falcon 9	Falcon 9
Payload-to-Launcher ratio	0.02478	0.03678
Re-entry [% survived mass]	45	0
Disposal	space	ocean

4.1.2 Earth Environmental Impact - Phase C+D

According to the ESA mission lifecycle convention, Phase C involves the detailed design of the satellite platform and its sub-systems, while Phase D covers manufacturing, integration, and testing activities in preparation for launch. Together, Phases C and D represent the most resource- and energy-intensive stages of spacecraft development, as they encompass the full realization of the physical hardware.

In this study, Phase C+D is of particular importance because it accounts for the upstream environmental impacts associated with the production and assembly of satellite components, especially those that vary between the two STRATHcube design scenarios. The CubeSat evaluated has been modelled using the latest available mass data and component breakdowns, ensuring that the environmental assessment reflects the current design baseline.

Notably, Scenario 2 incorporates an *ExPace cold-gas* propulsion system and a *GomSpace* onboard computer (OBC) to support active collision avoidance and post-mission disposal. The integration of the propulsion subsystem increases the satellite’s overall mass and system complexity, leading to elevated resource consumption and emissions during both the design and manufacturing stages.

Figure 3: Normalized environmental emissions-based impacts of STRATHcube components by category, shown as percentages compared to the baseline configuration.

Figure 4: Normalized environmental resources-based impacts of STRATHcube components by category, shown as percentages compared to the baseline configuration.

Under the CAM&PMD configuration, propulsion system components exhibit percentage rises across multiple environmental impact categories. Specifically, emissions-related impacts (Figure 3) show growths in *Climate Change* (6.67%), *Ionizing Radiation* (6.97%), and *Acidification* (~ 5.5%). These increases suggest that the propulsion subsystem is a not negligible contributor to these environmental pressures. The primary drivers are likely the energy-intensive manufacturing processes, the production and handling of propellants that emit greenhouse gases and acidifying substances, as well as materials or procedures associated with ionizing radiation during component fabrication or testing.

In terms of resource use (Figure 4), the most pronounced increases occur in *Water Use* (7.37%), *Total Cumulative Energy Demand* (6.7%), and *Resource Use, Fossils* (6.65%). This indicates that the propulsion system demands considerable water and energy inputs, alongside reliance on fossil-based materials. Contributing factors include cooling and cleaning operations during propulsion assembly, energy-intensive production of specialised propellant chemicals, and the dependence on fossil fuels and fossil-derived materials throughout manufacturing and testing phases. Conversely, some impact categories, such as *Human Toxicity* and *Particulate Matter* show negligible increases, reflecting the stringent controls in production environments and minimal release of toxic substances or particulate emissions.

Overall, these findings underscore the introduction of propulsion subsystem as a candidate driver in mission decision-making, particularly regarding energy demand, water use, and climate-related effects.

4.1.3 Earth Environmental Impact - Phase E1

Phase E1 of the mission lifecycle includes all launch-related operations and events, such as propellant consumption and engine testing firings. In this study, Falcon 9 is selected as the reference launcher due to its high reliability and the availability of detailed environmental data. Its capacity to deploy large numbers of CubeSats via ride-share missions makes it a representative and practical choice for constellation scenarios and ensures consistency with current industry practices.

Recalling Figure 2, both STRATHcube constellation configurations are assumed to be deployed in 10 shared launch events, with up to 100 satellites per launcher mission. Configuration 1 (*without* CAM&PMD) has a total payload mass of 272.6 kg on the vehicle, while Configuration 2 (*with* CAM&PMD) totals 404.6 kg. Given Falcon 9's LEO payload capacity of approximately 11,000 kg, these correspond to payload-to-launcher mass ratios of 0.02478 and 0.03678, respectively (Table 2). Although both ratios represent a small fraction of the vehicle's capacity, they provide a basis for proportionally attributing environmental impacts.

$$\left(\frac{\left(\frac{P}{L} \right)_{w/CAM\&PMD} - \left(\frac{P}{L} \right)_{w/o\ CAM\&PMD}}{\left(\frac{P}{L} \right)_{w/o\ CAM\&PMD}} \right) \times 100 \quad (12)$$

The percentual increment is calculated as the relative increase in payload-to-launcher ratio (Equation 12), as the difference in environmental impact between the two configurations during Phase E1 is driven entirely by the change in payload mass, since the launch system remains constant. Substituting the given values yields an approximate increase of 32.62%. This method assumes that launch-related impacts scale linearly with the share of payload mass, allowing a consistent and quantitative comparison of the environmental consequences of design changes.

4.1.4 Space Environmental Impact - Phase E2

Phase E2, as defined by the ESA, encompasses the operational lifetime of the satellite in orbit. Environmental considerations shift from terrestrial emissions to interactions within the orbital environment, with a focus on space traffic management and long-term orbital sustainability.

This study assesses the Orbital Risk (OR), the risk objects pose in a given orbital regime during a satellite's operational life, using the NESSY framework coupled with a launch traffic model. This combined approach allows for realistic estimation of collision probabilities and orbital congestion based on detailed mission parameters and traffic dynamics (Table 1).

As shown in Figure 5, during the operational period (roughly June 2029 to June 2034), the STRATHcube constellation *with* CAM&PMD capabilities (Scenario 2) achieves a significantly lower Orbital Risk of 0.00083574, compared to 0.00249257 in the baseline configuration *without* CAM&PMD (Scenario 1). This reduction results from enhanced active collision avoidance and controlled post-mission disposal capabilities, which reduce both the duration and likelihood of close conjunctions. The relative reduction in Orbital Risk is calculated analogously to the payload-to-launcher ratio increment (Equation 12), as follows:

$$\left(\frac{OR_{w/CAM\&PMD} - OR_{w/o\ CAM\&PMD}}{OR_{w/o\ CAM\&PMD}} \right) \times 100 \approx -66.45 \quad (13)$$

This notable decrease highlights the beneficial role of propulsion-enabled subsystems in improving orbital safety and promoting space sustainability by minimizing passive orbital exposure and enabling timely evasive manoeuvres aligned with debris mitigation guidelines.

Regarding Orbital Space Use, NESSY results indicate negligible differences between the two configurations. Given the equal number of satellites and the limited spatial footprint of the additional propulsion system, overall orbital crowding remains similar in both scenarios. Thus, while Scenario 2 substantially lowers Orbital Risk, its impact on orbital density is effectively negligible.

Figure 5: Temporal evolution of NESSY environmental indices through 2060 for three STRATHcube scenarios: no constellation launch, Configuration 1 (*without* CAM&PMD, blue), and Configuration 2 (*with* CAM&PMD, red). The curves highlight differences in orbital risk and spatial occupation over the mission lifetime.

4.1.5 Space Environmental Impact - Phase F

In this study, results computed using the NESSY framework (see Figure 5, after the end of operations in 2034) show that the STRATHcube configuration *without* CAM&PMD (Scenario 1) exhibits a higher Residual Orbital Risk (ROR) of approximately 0.00257, compared to 0.00113 for the configuration *with* CAM&PMD (Scenario 2). This substantial reduction, about -55.99% as calculated via the percentual increment expression in Equation 12, highlights the effectiveness of propulsion-enabled subsystems in reducing long-term collision risks through active post-mission disposal.

A similar trend is observed for Orbital Resource Depletion (ORD), which quantifies the long-term occupation of valuable orbital slots by non-functional objects. Scenario 1 yields a significantly higher depletion rate of approximately 3.33×10^{-8} objects/m³/year, compared to only 2.44×10^{-9} objects/m³/year in Scenario 2. This corresponds to a percentual reduction of approximately -92.79% , further confirming the benefit of controlled de-orbiting in preserving orbital capacity. Together, these results emphasize the critical role of end-of-life disposal strategies in maintaining a sustainable orbital environment.

4.1.6 Earth Environmental Impact – Phase F

Phase F of the mission life cycle encompasses post-mission disposal and end-of-life operations, thereby extending the environmental assessment beyond the orbital regime to include potential impacts on the Earth’s surface and atmosphere. Two critical parameters are quantified in this phase:

- *Mass Survival*: the fraction of spacecraft mass surviving atmospheric re-entry and depositing on Earth.
- *Disposal Pathway*: the environmental burden associated with the chosen final disposal strategy (e.g., controlled re-entry, ocean recovery, abandonment in orbit).

As defined in the mission scenarios (Section 4.1.1), the *without* CAM&PMD case involves an uncontrolled disposal path, while Scenario 2 (*with* CAM&PMD) features a controlled re-entry manoeuvre. Although these end-of-life strategies differ, the satellite platform is a CubeSat, and in both cases, it is highly unlikely that any residual mass will survive atmospheric re-entry or reach the Earth’s surface.

To estimate atmospheric emissions, the values in Table 2 are scaled based on the satellite mass difference between scenarios. This accounts for the increased material ablated and vaporised during re-entry of the heavier, CAM&PMD-equipped satellite. While the relationship between mass and emissions is not strictly linear, being influenced by geometry, velocity, and drag, in the absence of detailed re-entry modelling, linear or slightly sub-linear scaling is a common assumption in early-stage LCA. In this study, atmospheric emissions are conservatively assigned at 45% of full burn-up factors to the lighter satellite, reflecting a penalty for the lack of a targeted disposal strategy. This aligns with LCA principles that reward controlled end-of-life measures. Consequently, Scenario 2 incurs a proportional increase of approximately 45% in impact categories such as *Climate Change*, *Human Toxicity (cancer)*, and *Human Toxicity (non-cancer)*.

Figure 6: Environmental emissions-based impacts of STRATHcube disposal to space strategy by category.

Scenario 1 is nominally classified as “disposal to space.” In this context, disposal to space is considered to have no direct terrestrial environmental impact, as emissions and environmental burdens associated with this phase are assumed outside the scope of terrestrial impact assessment. Scenario 2 implements a controlled disposal strategy, directing re-entry targeting remote oceanic regions where, if any, surviving debris is assumed to be safely recovered. This approach involves an active manoeuvre to initiate disposal earlier, accelerating orbital decay and minimizing the time spent in low Earth orbit. Consequently, it reduces long-term risks to the space environment and limits the occupation of valuable orbital slots, contributing to more sustainable space operations.

The environmental impacts associated with the controlled disposal option (Scenario 2) are illustrated in Figure 6, depicting emissions-related effects by impact category. Reported values indicate the typical order of magnitude for each category, varying considerably as expressed using different units of measure.

4.2 STRATHcube CAM&PMD Trade-Off Considerations

This analysis presents a controlled comparison of the life cycle environmental impacts of a fixed satellite constellation architecture, evaluated under two operational strategies: one incorporating Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres and Post-Mission Disposal (CAM&PMD), and one excluding these measures. By isolating the effect of CAM&PMD, the LCA methodology highlights how end-of-life strategies influence mission-level environmental performance.

The evaluation produces two complementary result types:

- **Absolute impact values**, expressed in category-specific physical units (e.g., kg, CO₂, eq for *Climate Change*, CTUh for *Human Toxicity*), quantify the total burden attributable to each scenario.
- **Relative changes (in %)**, denoted as approximate percentage differences, highlight the proportional increase or decrease in impact between the two scenarios within each impact category.

This dual-layered approach enables robust intra-category comparisons across scenarios. Although direct comparisons across impact categories are not meaningful due to differing units and mechanisms, the method identifies where CAM&PMD induces the most significant relative shifts and which life cycle stages contribute most to overall burdens. These insights support informed design decisions, mitigation prioritization, and sustainability trade-offs.

4.2.1 Impact Scores Weighting Strategy

Building on the LCA results, a structured weighting system is introduced to consistently compare environmental impacts across categories, capturing both the effects of design choices and the relative magnitude of burdens throughout the mission.

A two-tiered weighting scheme is proposed:

- **Tier 1 – Inside Weights (Phase-Specific):** These reflect the relative sensitivity of each impact category within a given mission phase, based on the absolute value of the percentual variation due to CAM&PMD. For category c in phase p :

$$w_{\text{in}}^{(p,c)} = \frac{|\Delta_{\%}^{(p,c)}|}{\sum_{c'} |\Delta_{\%}^{(p,c')}|}$$

- **Tier 2 – Outside Weights (Cross-Phase Normalization):** These normalize each category's average absolute impact score $\bar{s}^{(c)}$ across the full life cycle:

$$w_{\text{out}}^{(c)} = \frac{\bar{s}^{(c)}}{\sum_{c'} \bar{s}^{(c')}}}$$

The combined weighting factor for each category c and phase p is defined as:

$$w_{\text{tot}}^{(p,c)} = w_{\text{in}}^{(p,c)} \cdot w_{\text{out}}^{(c)} \quad \text{with} \quad \sum_c w_{\text{tot}}^{(p,c)} = 1 \quad \forall p.$$

These weights capture both the differential sensitivity of impact categories to the inclusion of CAM&PMD systems and their absolute environmental relevance, as aggregated across all mission life cycle phases. The resulting values, presented in Appendix A, inform a holistic assessment framework that concurrently addresses terrestrial and orbital environmental dimensions. This dual-domain integration enhances the analytical rigour of sustainability evaluations in space mission design. In particular, the derived weights hold significant relevance for the architectural development of satellite constellations, where the replication of spacecraft units inherently magnifies environmental burdens. By providing a quantified basis for prioritizing impact categories, these results enable mission planners to incorporate sustainability criteria into early-stage trade-off analyses and system-level decision-making processes.

5. OB2 — Integrated Modelling Framework for Coupled Terrestrial and Orbital Environmental Impact Assessment

This study introduces an integrated modelling framework for predicting the coupled terrestrial and orbital environmental impacts associated with projected space traffic growth. The objective is to simultaneously assess the Earth-based effects of space activities, such as greenhouse gas emissions, resource depletion, and atmospheric pollution from satellite production and launches, and the long-term orbital consequences, including debris proliferation, collision probability, and orbital capacity saturation under varying traffic and mitigation policy scenarios.

The analysis builds on the forward-looking launch traffic model developed by Wilson et al. (2025),¹⁸ which synthesizes historical trends, commercial forecasts, and policy constraints. This model employs an exponential-logistic formulation to capture recent accelerations in launch activity and fits probability distributions to historical data to simulate the evolving frequency and characteristics of launched objects. Its parametric structure enables efficient scenario analysis of future traffic patterns and associated mission risks.

As a core input to this framework, the launch traffic model supports a dual analysis. First, it provides high-resolution projections of space objects' production and launch operations, enabling quantification of terrestrial environmental impacts. Second, it informs the assessment of orbital sustainability by estimating future collision risks and evaluating the efficacy of post-mission disposal (PMD) strategies.

This integrated methodology allows for a comprehensive assessment of environmental burdens across Earth and orbital domains. It supports scenario-based evaluation of future launch trajectories and mitigation policies, providing a systems-level understanding of how space traffic growth affects both planetary and orbital sustainability.

5.1 Earth Environmental Impact Assessment

This section introduces the methodology used to compute the terrestrial environmental impact scores associated with space activities. The assessment relies on detailed life cycle inventory data and impact characterization models to quantify emissions, resource consumption, and other relevant environmental indicators linked to satellites production and launches.

5.1.1 Launches Traffic Model

The future launch events schedule projection is generated by a data-driven scheduling algorithm that aligns predicted payload demands with available launch vehicle capabilities and operational constraints.

Data Inputs

- The Launch Traffic model represent a valid dataset detailing forecasted payload launches by month and year, including individual payload mass and target orbital inclination.
- The SSSD offers a list of Reference Launch Vehicles which are characterized by their typical low Earth orbit (LEO) payload capacities and standard inclination ranges, obtained by the database DISCOSweb by ESA (Table 3).

Table 3: SSSD LCA Data - Reference Launchers

The reference launchers have been selected by merging and overlapping the data available from the SSSD model and the DISCOSweb database by ESA. The ranges reflect the existence of different versions or configurations of the same launcher type.

Launch Vehicle	Mass [kg]	LEO Capacity [kg]	LEO Inclinations [degree]
Vega/Vega C	137,000 – 212,000	2,300	5, 97, 98.6
Atlas V	333,298 – 566,511	9,050 – 18,500	28.7, 51.6, 63.4
Falcon Heavy	1,420,788	63,800	28.5, 51.6, 63, 90
Falcon 9	389,000 – 538,000	11,000	28.5, 43, 51.6, 53, 66, 97, 145
Soyuz-FG	305,000	7,800	51.6, 64.8

Reference Launchers Emissions The environmental impact associated with each reference launch vehicle is evaluated by calculating the scores attributable to a single launch event, assuming a single-use launcher configuration. This impact assessment accounts just for emissions generated during the entire launch phase. The resulting score values provide a baseline for comparing the relative environmental burdens of different launch vehicles on a per-launch basis. These single-event impacts serve as fundamental inputs for projecting cumulative environmental consequences under varying launch demand scenarios.

Figure 7: Earth Environmental Impact Scores per single launch event across reference launch vehicles.

Payload Grouping Payloads are grouped according to their planned launch month and target orbital inclination, which is rounded to the nearest 0.1 degrees. This binning approach reflects realistic operational practices by clustering payloads that share similar temporal and orbital requirements. To maximize launcher utilization and align with contemporary launch strategies, it is assumed that payloads within each bin are compatible for shared deployment on the same launch vehicle, an approach commonly referred to as *ride-share*. This assumption reflects the growing prevalence of ride-share missions, particularly for small satellites and constellation deployments.

Launcher Matching and Capacity Optimization For each payload group, the algorithm performs the following steps:

- Select launch vehicles with typical LEO inclination ranges compatible within a tolerance of $\pm 1.5^\circ$.
- Enforce a maximum of two launches per vehicle per month to reflect operational limitations.
- Sort payloads by descending mass and assign them in batches to launchers, maximizing total payload mass utilization without exceeding launcher capacity.

If payloads remain unassigned after the initial matching, they are allocated to the closest compatible launch vehicle by capacity and inclination, prioritizing vehicles with available monthly launch slots. The resulting launch schedule in Figure 8 provides a detailed, temporally resolved projection of launch activity from 2025 to 2060.

Figure 8: Projected annual launch demand by vehicle type from 2025 to 2060 based on the model assumptions.

Launch Events Model The increasing launch demand observed for certain vehicles, such as *Vega* exhibiting a steep growth up to approximately 1000 launches per year by 2060, can be attributed to several key factors, related to the assumptions: a high volume of small payloads present in the traffic input data, the suitability of the launcher for low-inclination orbits, positioning it as the optimal ride-share candidate within the model framework. The model’s prioritization of mass efficiency, which assigns payload batches that maximize each launcher’s capacity utilization, thereby necessitating small, frequent launches. *Atlas variants*, *Falcon 9*, and *Soyuz-FG* maintain moderate and stable launch rates, reflecting their specialized roles in specific inclination bands or payload size categories. *Heavy launchers* such as *Falcon Heavy* are seldom used, due to their large capacity being difficult to efficiently fill within monthly operational constraints.

These assumptions align with current trends in space transportation, where light- and medium-lift launchers constitute the backbone for an increasing number of frequent and distributed launches, particularly for low Earth orbit (LEO) constellations and small satellite missions.

Annual Launches Environmental Impact Computation To estimate the environmental impact of launch activities, the Earth Environmental Impact scores per single launch event (Figure 7) are multiplied by the projected annual launch counts per vehicle type derived from the launch traffic model (Figure 8). This aggregation yields annual environmental impact scores by launcher category, accounting for the temporal evolution of launch demand and vehicle utilization. This approach enables the assessment of future environmental burdens associated with evolving launch traffic scenarios, facilitating impact mitigation analysis and sustainable space operations planning.

5.1.2 CAM&PMD Sub-Systems Production

To assess the environmental burden of the propulsion sub-system, a component-level life cycle impact assessment (LCA) is conducted using detailed process data extracted from the SSSD.

Unit Design Model and Mass Allocation The propulsion subsystem is decomposed into its primary hardware components: Thruster, Tank, and Propulsion Feed System, as well as its propellant (HPGP/LMP-103S). Each component is assigned a relative mass share based on sub-system design estimates, reflecting its contribution to the total unit weight. The intermediate output consists of environmental impact scores per kilogram of subsystem mass for emissions and resource use. Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the relative contribution of each propulsion component to the overall impact per unit mass.

Figure 9: Relative contribution of propulsion sub-system components to each emissions-related impact category. Results are normalized to show the percentage contribution of each component per category.

Figure 10: Relative contribution of propulsion sub-system components to each resource use-related impact category. Values are expressed as percentage shares of the total impact within each category.

Sub-system-Level Production Impact Projection Across Lunch Traffic Payloads To extend the subsystem-level environmental assessment to the future scenario, the calculated impact intensities are propagated to individual payloads within the launch traffic model. Payloads are filtered from the launch dataset based on two criteria: mass below 100 kg and presence of manoeuvring capability. The mass threshold reflects the assumption that medium-to-large spacecraft generally include propulsion systems capable of CAM&PMD, with associated propellant mass accounted for separately. Manoeuvring capability is assigned according to the assumed mitigation policy, isolating payloads likely equipped with CAM&PMD subsystems.

For each selected payload, the CAM&PMD subsystem mass is estimated as 10% of the payload mass, consistent with typical small satellite propulsion mass fractions. Impact factors (expressed per kg of subsystem) are then scaled by the relative mass to quantify the environmental burden attributable to CAM&PMD on a per-payload basis. These values are integrated into the original launch dataset, enabling time-resolved analysis of sub-system-specific environmental impacts across all planned missions.

5.2 Space Environmental Impact Assessment

This section presents two representative examples to illustrate the differences in space environmental impact under different static policies, assuming launch rate from 2023 to 2063 are the same for both cases. Simulations are conducted with CAM implementation rates of 100% and 50%. Figure 11 shows the evolution of global connectivity, denoted by α^n , over the next 40 years. Figure 12 presents the local connectivity, α_t^n , within the orbital regime defined by altitudes between 500 and 550 km and inclination bins between 0° and 60°. Given the stochastic behaviour of the evolution of the space environment, both Figure 11 and Figure 12 show the mean values with the solid curves while the standard deviation with the shaded area.

Simulation results suggest that a higher CAM rate leads to a reduced impact on the space environment from both global and local connectivity perspectives. This is because a higher CAM rate decreases the likelihood of satellite colliding with other objects. The difference in global connectivity between the two CAM scenarios is not significant during the first ten years. However, by the end of the 40-year period, global connectivity under the 100% CAM scenario reaches approximately 0.12, compared to 0.142 under the 50% CAM scenario, an increase of about 16%. In contrast, local connectivity appears more sensitive to changes in CAM policy, offering deeper insight into the orbital risk induced by specific orbital regimes. After 40 years, the local connectivity under the 100% CAM scenario is approximately 0.085, while under the 50% CAM scenario it rises to around 0.115, an increase of about 30%.

Figure 11: Comparison of global connectivity α^n .

Figure 12: Comparison of local connectivity α_t^n .

5.3 Reinforcement Learning Block

Figure 13 illustrates a reinforcement learning (RL)-based framework designed to optimize the environmental impact of future space activities. At the core of the system is the RL agent, which interacts with the environment by receiving observations and rewards, and taking actions accordingly. These actions involve setting launch traffic parameters (A , b) and implementing specific policies (such as Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres (CAM) and Post-Mission Disposal (PMD)). The agent's decisions feed into the Future Space Activity module, which includes a Launch Traffic Model and a Launches Model. These models simulate space objects (*with* or *without* CAM) and launch activity over time. The outputs are then passed to the Total Impacts Calculator, which quantifies both space-based and Earth-based environmental impacts. This calculator includes NESSY for space impact assessment and LCA for evaluating Earth-based impacts. The MCDA (Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis) module aggregates these impact scores to produce a final Environmental Impact Score, which is then returned to the agent as a reward. This feedback loop allows the RL agent to learn and adapt its strategy over time, optimizing space traffic management in a way that minimizes environmental impact on both Earth and space. As shown in Algorithm 1, the reinforcement learning framework integrates both NESSY and LCA to optimize sustainable launch rate and space policy over time.

Algorithm 1: Reinforcement Learning with NESSY and LCA for Space Sustainability

Input: Initial population state s_0 in year 2025;
Time horizon T
Output: Trained launch rate and space policy $\pi(a_t|s_t)$
Initialize s_0 ;
for $t = 0, 1, \dots, T$ **do**
 Select action $a_t \sim \pi(a_t|s_t)$;
 Generate launch schedule Λ_t using a_t ;
 Run NESSY to compute space impact scores α_t ;
 Run LCA to compute Earth impact scores v_t ;
 Compute reward R_t by Eq. (11);
 Simulate forward to obtain next state s_{t+1} ;
return trained launch rate and space policy $\pi(a_t|s_t)$

Figure 13: Diagram of Reinforcement Learning Block

In this paper, the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm is applied to train the RL agent due to its stability and efficiency of handling continuous action spaces. PPO is a policy gradient method that improves training stability by clipping the policy update to prevent large deviations (Equation 14).

$$L^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\min \left(r_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}_t \right) \right] \quad (14)$$

where

- $L^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta)$: The clipped objective function used to update the policy parameters θ .
- $\mathbb{E}_t[\cdot]$: Expectation over timesteps t , averages the objective across sampled trajectories.
- $r_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(a_t|s_t)}$: The probability ratio between the new policy and the old policy, indicating how much the current policy has changed.
- \hat{A}_t : The estimated advantage function, representing how much better (or worse) an action is compared to the average.
- $\text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)$: A clipping function that constrains the probability ratio to the range $[1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon]$, to avoid overly large updates.

At each step, the agent observes the state s_t , which represents the current space environment, including information of all objects and their associated physical and orbital parameters. Table 4 presents an example of the format of a population list with 18.346 objects used in NESSY simulation. However, obtaining complete information about all objects for training the agent is not practical. Therefore, instead of observing the full population list at each step, a lower-dimensional observation vector is defined to provide a compact and informative representation of the space environment state. Specifically, at each time step, the observation is given by:

$$s_t = [t, x_P(t), x_U(t), x_N(t), x_F(t)] \quad (15)$$

where $x_P(t)$, $x_U(t)$, $x_N(t)$ and $x_F(t)$ represent the number of payloads, upper stages, non-maneuverable satellites and fragments at time t , respectively.

Table 4: An example of the population list used in NESSY

ID	a	e	i	bstar	mass	radius	alt	ctrl	life	launch	class	node
1	7261.6	0.0936	28.05	8.47e-4	1840	0.0030	200	0	0	2.4530e6	2	2
2	6683.8	0.0102	58.47	0.3367	130	0.0014	200	0	0	2.4384e6	2	5
3	6598.1	8.93e-4	53.21	5.18e-4	1	1.22e-4	200	0	0	2.4596e6	3	3
4	6612.9	7.73e-4	51.63	0.0013	4	1.72e-4	200	0	0	2.4579e6	4	4
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
18346	1.6420e4	0.5941	26.8517	5.111e-4	4300	0.0036	2200	0	0	2.4599e6	2	5

The action vector a_t is

$$a_t = [A, b, k] \tag{16}$$

where A and b are parameters that govern the launch rate, as described in.¹⁸ The launch rate is modeled by the following equation:

$$N(t) = n_0 + \frac{A \cdot \exp(d(t - t_0))}{b + \exp(-c(t - t_0))} \tag{17}$$

where $t_0 = 2023$, $c = 0.2$, $d = 0.0001$ and $n_0 = 150$. The parameter k represents the proportion of newly launched objects with mass less than 100 kg that are maneuverable in a given year. The reward function is defined as:

$$R_t = -w_1 \cdot I_{\text{Earth}}(t) - w_2 \cdot I_{\text{Space}}(t) + w_3 \cdot I_{\text{Benefits}}(t) \tag{18}$$

where $I_{\text{Earth}}(t)$ represents the Earth-based environmental impact, such as *Climate Change*, *Water Use*, etc. $I_{\text{Space}}(t)$ represents the space-based environmental impact such as the local/global connectivity factor proposed in this paper. $I_{\text{Benefits}}(t)$ represents the benefits generated by the launched missions, such as revenues from satellite services (e.g., communication, remote sensing, and navigation), and scientific outcomes, etc. The weights vector $w = [w_1, w_2, w_3]$ specifies the relative importance of each component. To improve computational efficiency during agent training, a surrogate model f is pre-trained such that

$$[R_t, s_{t+1}] = f(s_t, a_t) \tag{19}$$

Considering $A \in [1200, 1800]$, $b \in [0.1, 0.5]$ and $k \in [50, 100]\%$, the following examples showcase how the proposed RL framework is used to optimize the space policy and launch schedule between 2025 and 2030. The objective is to achieve low I_{Earth} (quantified by *Climate Change*), low I_{Space} (quantified by local connectivity factor α_i^n), and high $I_{\text{Benefits}}(t)$ (quantified by *Launch rate* Λ) over next 40 years. A reference case uses the following static parameters: $A = 1200$, $b = 0.1$, $c = 0.2$, $d = 0.0001$, $t_0 = 2023$, $n_0 = 150$ and $k = 100$, which corresponds to the scenario with the lowest space environmental impact due to the high manoeuvrability ratio for a given launch rate. To illustrate the long-term effect across different impact categories, the cumulative *Climate Change*, cumulative *Launch Rate* and temporal local connectivity are presented, showing how these scores evolve over time.

Assuming a weight vector $w = [0, 1, 0]$, which indicates that the agent priorities minimizing space environmental impacts, Figure 14 and Figure 15 compare the optimized launch traffic and the corresponding long-term impacts with those of the reference scenario. As a results, both space-based and Earth-based environmental impacts are reduced, primarily due to a lower launch rate. This result highlights the importance of incorporating benefits into the reward function; otherwise, the trained agent will consistently favour actions that minimize the launch rate, potentially compromising benefits.

Assuming an alternative weight vector $w = [5 \times 10^{-8}, 5 \times 10^6, 1]$, Figure 16 and Figure 17 compare the optimized launch traffic with the reference scenario. The simulation results suggest that the increase of mission benefits inevitably leads to a rise in both space and Earth environmental impacts, underscoring the trade-off between maximizing benefits and maintaining environmental sustainability.

Figure 14: Comparison of launch rate.

Figure 15: Comparison of scores.

Figure 16: Comparison of launch rate.

Figure 17: Comparison of scores.

6. Conclusions

This study presents an integrated framework that combines the NESSY tool with the SSSD methodology, enabling a comprehensive assessment of space mission impacts across both terrestrial and orbital domains. Two case studies demonstrate the framework’s potential to inform environmentally responsible space mission design.

Applied to the STRATHcube constellation, OB1 investigates the trade-off between minimizing Earth-based environmental impacts by omitting a propulsion system and enhancing mission functionality through its inclusion for collision avoidance and end-of-life disposal. The analysis reveals that while propulsion increases the environmental burden on Earth, it is essential for ensuring long-term orbital sustainability. The comparison between the CAM&PMD configuration and the non-propulsion scenario provides a quantitative basis for future mission designers to assign relative weights to different impact categories and system priorities. This enables more informed decisions when balancing environmental performance, mission safety, and compliance with space debris mitigation guidelines, particularly relevant in the context of large satellite constellations in LEO.

OB2 examines how various launch traffic and related space policy scenarios influence the evolution of the space environment and affect cumulative impacts on both Earth and space. These results underscore the importance of integrated, forward-looking assessments to guide sustainable design under increasing space activity and regulatory pressure. As part of OB2, the proposed Reinforcement Learning (RL) block further demonstrate that autonomous policy optimization can successfully balance trade-offs between environmental and space progress objectives. When the reward function prioritizes only space impact, the RL agent minimizes launch rates, leading to reductions in both orbital and terrestrial impacts but at the expense of benefits. Conversely, when the positive return performance is weighted, the optimized policy increases launch activity, boosting revenues but also amplifying environmental impacts.

These findings highlight the need for a balanced, multi-objective reward structure to support sustainability-aware space traffic strategies.

Future steps will involve extending the framework from traditional LCA to LCSA in both objectives by testing the feasibility of incorporating economic and social dimensions alongside traditional LCA impact categories and the newly developed global space health indicators via MCDA. The complete set of quantified impacts will serve as input for defining the reward function in a reinforcement learning block, supporting automated, sustainability-aware mission architecture optimization. Together, these developments advance the foundation for a systemic and scalable approach to sustainable space system design.

A. Impact Categories Weights

Table 5: Phase C+D

Type	Impact Category	Inside Weight	Outside Weight	Normalized Weight
emission	Acidification	0.088305489	0.097956266	0.073490385
emission	Air acidification	0.088782816	0.097967091	0.073895796
emission	Climate change	0.106125696	0.085004677	0.076643262
emission	Human toxicity, non-cancer	0.000159109	0.995460523	0.001345641
emission	Ionising radiation	0.110898966	0.050112535	0.047215487
emission	Ozone depletion	0.085759745	0.084995549	0.061928458
emission	Particulate matter	0.000159109	0.995308287	0.001345436
emission	Photochemical ozone formation	0.072553699	0.229541713	0.141491966
resources	Critical raw materials	0.029753381	0.328262978	0.082979121
resources	Land use	0.087032617	0.122282530	0.090418451
resources	Resource use, fossils	0.105807478	0.127237246	0.114377665
resources	Resource use, minerals and metals, reserve base	0.000636436	0.969108373	0.005240077
resources	Resource use, minerals and metals, ultimate reserve	0.000159109	0.992149263	0.001341165
resources	Total cumulative energy demand	0.106603023	0.068686052	0.062208349
resources	Water use	0.117263325	0.166702162	0.166078740

Table 6: Phase E1

Type	Impact Category	Inside Weight	Outside Weight	Normalized Weight
emission	Acidification	0.0625	0.895435743	0.093610062
emission	Air acidification	0.0625	0.896127596	0.093682389
emission	Climate change	0.0625	0.914987179	0.095653995
emission	Human toxicity, cancer	0.0625	0.000320245	0.000033479
emission	Human toxicity, non-cancer	0.0625	0.004434537	0.000463593
emission	Ionising radiation	0.0625	0.949887465	0.099302518
emission	Ozone depletion	0.0625	0.915003806	0.095655733
emission	Particulate matter	0.0625	0.004691145	0.000490419
emission	Photochemical ozone formation	0.0625	0.759133804	0.079360873
resources	Critical raw materials	0.0625	0.671737022	0.070224295
resources	Land use	0.0625	0.877717470	0.091757770
resources	Resource use, fossils	0.0625	0.872762754	0.091239797
resources	Resource use, minerals and metals, reserve base	0.0625	0.030891627	0.003229452
resources	Resource use, minerals and metals, ultimate reserve	0.0625	0.007850737	0.000820727
resources	Total cumulative energy demand	0.0625	0.931313948	0.097360818
resources	Water use	0.0625	0.833297838	0.087114081

Table 7: Phases E2

Type	Impact Category	Inside Weight	Outside Weight	Normalized Weight
space	Orbital Risk	1.000000000	0.424946636	1.000000000

Table 8: Phase F

Type	Impact Category	Inside Weight	Outside Weight	Normalized Weight
emission	Climate change	0.333333333	0.000007781	0.000961
emission	Human toxicity, cancer	0.333333333	0.002585077	0.319408
emission	Human toxicity, non-cancer	0.333333333	0.000104923	0.012964
emission	Acidification	0.142857143	0.006607991	0.092396
emission	Air acidification	0.142857143	0.005905313	0.082571
emission	Climate change	0.142857143	0.000000363	0.000005
emission	Ozone depletion	0.142857143	0.000000645	0.000009
emission	Particulate matter	0.142857143	0.000000568	0.000008
emission	Photochemical ozone formation	0.142857143	0.011324483	0.158344
space	Orbital Risk	0.376327463	0.575053364	0.281899
space	Orbital Space Use	0.623672537	0.063310846	0.051434

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